

Deliverable D3.3

5G-PPP security enablers SW release (v1.0)

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Executive summary

This document accompanies the delivery of first software of 5G ENSURE namely v1.0 (also called R1) due M11 (Sep'16). For each of the enablers planned for R1 and having features (as per Technical Roadmap cf. D3.1 [1]), the software is delivered in conformance of the open specifications previously released (cf. D3.2 [2]). Overall this short document provides for each enabler the characteristics of software delivery like version, owner, format, delivery repository but gives also details for deploying and running it like execution environment, documentation and bugs tracking.

This deliverable (i.e. D3.3) focusing on software delivery of first set of security enablers from 5G-ENSURE is delivered same time that the manuals accompanying these enablers is delivered (i.e. D3.4 [3]).

This closes the work on first release where first set of enablers where planned (through Technical Roadmap – D3.1 [1]), openly specified (i.e. D3.2 [2]), developed and released (this deliverable i.e. D3.3) and documented (through couple of manuals in the context of D3.4 [3]).

Enablers software released here would be now integrated/deployed and tested/assessed on the 5G Security Testbed (in scope of WP4).

Foreword

5G-ENSURE belongs to the first group of EU-funded projects which collaboratively develop 5G under the umbrella of the 5G Infrastructure Public Private Partnership (5G-PPP) in the Horizon 2020 Programme. The overall goal of 5G-ENSURE is to deliver strategic impact across technology and business enablement, standardisation and vision for a secure, resilient and viable 5G network. The project covers research & innovation - from technical solutions (5G security architecture and testbed with 5G security enablers) to market validation and stakeholders engagement - spanning various application domains.

This document describes the software delivery of the R1 security enablers. These enablers were described in [1] and specified in [2].

This deliverable is strongly linked with [3], which provides the enablers' user and installation guides.

Disclaimer

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Abbreviations

5G-PPP	5G Infrastructure Public Private Partnership
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
IoT	Internet of Things
LTE	Long Term Evolution
OS	Operating System
OSS	Open Source Software
R1	Release 1
SDLC	Software Development Life Cycle
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

1.1 Approach of this report

This document describes a part of the SDLC applied to 5G Ensure Security enablers. The different steps in this SDLC are described in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Software Development Life Cycle of R1 Security Enablers

In this cycle the different steps are associated with 5G-ENSURE documents, there are:

- Technical roadmap, describing the goal of each security enabler and their contribution to the different use cases described in [4]. This roadmap is described in [1].
- Open specifications giving more details about the goal of the different enablers and their designs. These specifications are gathered in [2].
- Implementations, implementing the enablers themselves. The details for using them are given in this document associated with the enabler documentation [3]
- Deployment and Verification, checking that the enablers, after their deliveries, can be deployed and run following their Open Specifications (in scope of WP4).

The main objective of this document is to give all necessary information regarding the implementation and how to deploy and run the v1.0/R1 Security enablers.

1.2 Intended audience

This document is firstly to provide an orderly report to the EC, describing the Release 1 Software delivery (namely v1.0) with all details for each enabler.

It aims secondly to be the reference document for WP4 where all enablers will be deployed in the testbed and tested/assessed. It contains all information for deploying the enablers and all pointers for documentations and for raising bugs during the test phase.

Thirdly, this document will help the 5G PPP ecosystem who may benefit from an overview of Release 1/v1.0 in a summarized manner. Three groups in this ecosystem could take benefits of this release:

- 5G-ENSURE consortium where all partners could be interested. In this case, [4] gives the rules for using them.
- 5G PPP where all partners involved could want to test or evaluate these security enablers in their 5G projects. In this case, [5] gives the rules for using them.
- External actors interested by 5G security and interested by the different security enablers. No specific rules are defined at this stage but these actors could interact with the different enabler owners.

This document is a snapshot of the software delivered at M11 but the different versions and some existing information could evolve depending mainly on bug fixing.

A new iteration, called R2 (or v2.0 software release) will take place after this release and a part of the R1 Security enablers will be continued with new features while fully new security enablers will be added.

2 Summary of the release

The description of the software release is provided through a web page shared by the 5G Ensure consortium:

[https://workspace.vtt.fi/sites/5g-ensure/SitePages/5G ENSURE-Software Delivery information for R1.aspx](https://workspace.vtt.fi/sites/5g-ensure/SitePages/5G%20ENSURE-Software%20Delivery%20information%20for%20R1.aspx)

The following figure gives a screenshot of a part of this web page while an export of this table is given in Table 1.

Enabler Name	Owner	Version	Code repository	Software repository*	Delivery format	Execution environment	Guides*	Bugs tracking
<i>Internet of things - IOT</i>	SICS	1.0.0	NA	groupaka-0.1.deb	Debian package	Linux 14.04 LTE + Kernel 3.19	T31_IoTEabler .pdf	IoT bug tracking
<i>Fine-grained Authorization</i>	TASE TS	1.0.0	NA	FineGrainedAuthorizationEnabler-0.1.zip	zip	Ubuntu Server 16.04.1 LTS	T31_FineGrainedAuthorization.pdf	Bug Tracking

Figure 2: Webpage sharing R1 delivery information for the consortium

The details given by the table are:

Enabler name: The name of the enabler.

Owner: The partner in charge of the enabler.

Version: The version of the software delivered.

Code repository: In the case of OSS delivery, the source code repository must be given and publicly available.

Software repository: A link to the place where the software is delivered. This place can be managed by the partner but should be accessible for all partners and for the project reviewers.

Delivery format: The format of the delivery allowing its deployment.

Execution environment: The main OS characteristics needed for the enabler execution.

Guides: A link to Installation and Administration Guide, User and Programmer Guide and Unit Test delivered in the context of [3].

Bug tracking: A link to a tool managing the bugs rise during the deployment and the verification phase of the enabler.

Use terms & conditions: a link or a description explaining how anyone outside 5G PPP partners could use the enabler.

Table 1: R1 delivery description

Enabler Name	Owner	Version	Code repository	Software repository†	Delivery format	Execution environment	Guides*	Bugs tracking	Use terms & conditions
<i>Internet of things - IOT</i>	SICS	1.0.0	NA	groupaka-0.1.deb	Debian package	Linux 14.04 LTE + Kernel 3.19	T31_IoTEabler.pdf	IoT bug tracking	OAI terms and conditions applies. For external usage outside 5G-Ensure please ask: rosario.giustolisi@sics.se
<i>Fine-grained Authorization</i>	TASETS	1.0.0	NA	FineGrainedAuthorization-RCD.v01_00_00.zip FineGrainedAuthorization.v01_00_00.zip	zip	Ubuntu Server 16.04.1 LTS	T31_FineGrainedAuthorization.pdf	Bug Tracking	For external usage outside 5G-Ensure perimeter, please ask: gorka.lendrinovela@thalesenia.space.com sebastien.keller@thalesgroup.com
<i>Privacy Enhanced Identity Protection</i>	TIIT	1.0	NA	libkpabe-1.0.tar.gz	tar.gz	Linux Ubuntu version >= 14.0	T32_PrivacyEnhancedIdentityProtection.pdf	PrivacyEnhancedIdentityProtection BugTracking	For external usage outside 5G-Ensure perimeter, please ask: luciana.costa@it.telecomitalia.it madalina.baltatu@it.telecomitalia.it
<i>Device identifier(s) privacy</i>	Oxford	1.0	NA	dhcpcd-dip.v1.0.tar.gz	tar.gz	Linux Ubuntu 16.04	T32_DeviceIdentifierPrivacy.pdf	Issue tracker	For external usage outside of 5G-Ensure, please ask: piers.ohanlon@cs.ox.ac.uk

Trust Builder	IT-INNOV	1.0	NA	TrustBuilder v1.0.zip	zip	Linux Ubuntu 16.04	T33_TrustBuilder.pdf	Issue tracker	For external usage outside of the 5G-ENSURE perimeter, please ask: ms@it-innovation.soton.ac.uk
Trust Metric Enabler	VTT	1.0	NA	Trust Metric Enabler.zip	zip	Linux Ubuntu 16.04	T33_Trust metric enabler.pdf	Trust Metric Bug Tracking	Please ask: Pekka.Ruuska@vtt.fi
VNF Certification	TCS	1.0	NA	VNF Certification Factory 0.1	tar.gz war	Linux 14.04 LTE	T33_VNFCertification.pdf	VNF Certification Bug Tracking	For external usage outside of 5G-Ensure perimeter, please ask: sebastien.keller@thalesgroup.com
Security Monitor for 5G Micro-Segments	VTT	0.1	NA	MicroSegmentMonitor 1.0.tgz	tar.gz	Linux	T34_MicroSegmentMonitor.pdf	Issue tracker	For external usage outside of 5G-Ensure perimeter, please ask: Jani.Suomalainen@vtt.fi
Generic Collector Interface	Orange	0.1	NA	GenericCollectorInterface.zip	zip	Linux Ubuntu 14.04	T34_GenericCollectorInterface.pdf	GenericCollectorInterface Bug Tracking	Please ask: jeanphilippe.wary@orange.com
PuSAR: Proactive Security Analysis and Remediation	TS	1.0	NA	PuSAR	docker	Linux Ubuntu 16.04	T34_PuSAR.pdf	PuSAR Bug Tracking	For external usage outside of 5G-Ensure perimeter, please ask: Olivier.Bettan@thalesgroup.com
System Security State repository	IT-INNOV	1.0	NA	5G-ENSURE Asset Model v1.0.zip	zip	NA	T34 System Security State Repository v1.0 Release Note	Issue tracker	For external usage outside of the 5G-ENSURE perimeter, please ask: ms@it-innovation.soton.ac.uk
Satellite Network Monitoring	TASE	1.0.0	NA	SatelliteNetworkMonitoring.v01_00_00.zip	zip	Ubuntu Server 16.04.1 LTS	T34_SatelliteNetworkMonitoring.pdf	Bug Tracking	For external usage outside 5G-Ensure perimeter, please ask: gorka.lendrinovela@thalesaleniaspace.com
Access Control Mechanisms	NEC	1.0	NA	https://dav.neclab.eu/5GENSURE/	Debian package	Linux Ubuntu >=14.04	T35_AccessControlMechanisms.pdf	Bug Tracking	For external usage outside 5G-Ensure perimeter, please ask: felix.klaedtke@neclab.eu
Component-Interaction Audits	NEC	1.0	NA	https://dav.neclab.eu/5GENSURE/	binary	Linux, e.g. Linux Ubuntu >=14.04	T35_ComponentInteractionAudits.pdf	Bug Tracking	For external usage outside 5G-Ensure perimeter, please ask: felix.klaedtke@neclab.eu
Bootstrapping Trust	SICS	1.0	NA	BootstrappingTrust.tgz	deb, tar.gz	Linux Ubuntu >=14.04	T35_BootstrappingTrust.pdf	BootstrappingTrust Bug Tracking	Please ask: nicolae@sics.se

				openvswitch-tswitch_1-1_amd64.deb					
<i>Micro-segmentation</i>	VTT	1.0	NA	microsegmentation_1_0.tbz2	tbz2	Linux Ubuntu version >= 14.04	T35_MicroSegmentation.pdf	Issue Tracker	Please ask: Kimmo.Ahola@vtt.fi Olli.Mammela@vtt.fi

3 Complementary information

Further details about the security enablers can be found in the following documents:

- [1] provides the roadmap of the enablers,
- [6] describes the 5G use cases delivered by the consortium,
- [2] provides the open specification for the enablers,
- [3] contains the Installation and Administration Guide, User and Programmer Guide and Unit Tests, and
- [7] describing the testbed architecture where the enablers will be deployed and assessed.

References

- [1] 5.-E. Consortium, "D3.1 5G-PPP security enablers technical roadmap (early vision)," 2016.
- [2] 5.-E. Consortium, "D3.2 5G-PPP security enablers open specifications (v1.0)," 2016.
- [3] 5.-E. Consortium, "D3.4 5G-PPP Security Enablers Documentation (v1.0)," 2016.
- [4] 5. E. Consortium, "Consortium Agreement," 2015.
- [5] 5. PPP, "Collaboration agreement".
- [6] 5.-E. Consortium, "D4.1 5G Security testbed architecture," 2016.
- [7] 5.-E. Consortium, "D2.1 Use cases," 2016.